

TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND THEIR ORAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract: This article highlights the benefits of employing interactive methods in teaching Russian as a foreign language, focusing on their positive impact on both content mastery and student development. Interactive approaches foster strong teacher-student relationships, facilitate knowledge retention through shared information and active learning, and cultivate essential communication skills like expression and idea exchange. The interactive nature of these lessons encourages independent thinking, observation, and active participation, leading to enhanced critical thinking and logical reasoning skills.

Key words: Pedagogical technologies, discursive competence, multilingual dictionaries, method, information, practice, knowledge, interactive teaching.

Introduction

The goal of modern education is to produce highly skilled professionals adept in all fields of knowledge. This necessitates the integration of contemporary information technologies into foreign language instruction. The use of modern teaching aids, language classrooms, multimedia, specialized software, and multilingual electronic dictionaries is paramount in achieving this goal.

The incorporation of various teaching methods, the press, telecommunications, and the internet in foreign language instruction serves not only as a source of language learning but also as a catalyst for intellectual development. Among the most effective approaches is distance learning through information and communication technologies. Computer technology offers unparalleled opportunities for language acquisition through internet-based platforms, including:

- * Practical application of acquired communication skills in real-life scenarios.
- * Development of adaptive language use based on changing communication situations.
- * Creation of strong motivation and a genuine desire to engage in authentic conversation and speech study.
- * Overcoming psychological barriers, particularly fear of speaking a foreign language and making mistakes.
- * High-quality and immediate effectiveness of education.
- * Mastering a significant number of new words, speech patterns, and common speech events in a single session.

This approach fosters a dynamic and engaging learning environment, encouraging learners to utilize the language they are acquiring effectively and confidently. While extensive vocabulary and language knowledge are not prerequisites for engaging in basic online conversations, the amount of language one possesses directly impacts the quality and depth of their communication. To effectively participate in a conversation, individuals need a minimum level of language proficiency.

The primary goal of this training course is to equip learners with the ability to listen and speak in the target language. This focus on oral communication is further expanded to encompass written forms of communication, including reading and writing.

Expanding the learning objectives of this course allows for the activation and refinement of previously acquired speaking skills. It also aims to develop higher-level communicative competencies and systematically reinforce users' grammatical understanding. The effectiveness of this educational approach lies in its ability to enhance information retention, broaden awareness, and ultimately lead to improved learning outcomes.

Despite its advantages, distance learning presents some unique challenges. Choosing an appropriate teaching method tailored specifically to this format is

crucial. The success of any educational system depends heavily on the effectiveness of the methods employed.

Therefore, defining the concept of "teaching method" is critical. A teaching method is essentially a structured interaction between teachers and students, designed to achieve educational goals effectively in a modern context. Today, fluency in foreign languages, particularly English, is a vital requirement for professional success. Uzbekistan's education system is actively implementing a scientific approach to English language teaching, incorporating new information and communication technologies to meet the demands of the modern world.

The need for foreign language proficiency in today's world necessitates the development of innovative teaching methods tailored for younger generations. These methods should align with the "National Training Program" and be implemented effectively in the learning process. Uzbekistan's distance learning system demonstrates significant potential for success and should be widely adopted.

Our country is actively working towards building an information society, incorporating advanced information and communication technologies across all sectors. Interactive services play a crucial role in this process. Scientists have developed and validated interactive methods for teaching foreign languages, proving their effectiveness over traditional approaches. Interactive methods engage students through active participation and collaboration. The term "interactive" emphasizes the learner's active role in the process.

Interactive lessons foster creativity, encourage active information sharing, facilitate free expression of ideas, promote initiative-taking, and encourage collaborative problem-solving. They empower students to share ideas in writing and contribute to the learning environment.

In the context of educational innovation, interactive methods are increasingly seen as essential. Interactivity is characterized by two-way communication, where learning occurs through conversations, dialogues, and student-teacher interactions.

The primary aim of interactive methods is to create an environment that fosters active and independent thinking, optimizing learning conditions. This approach unlocks students' intellectual potential and enhances the quality and effectiveness of education. Interactive lessons are designed to ensure every student participates actively, expressing their knowledge and perspectives openly.

The distance learning system facilitates two-way communication and student interaction. In this setting, the exchange of information between students is often more intense than between student and teacher, highlighting the importance of providing email addresses to all participants for effective communication.

Interactive methods offer numerous advantages, most notably the development of strong communication skills. Their application in foreign language instruction enhances student participation and motivates them to achieve optimal results. Furthermore, they enable teachers to introduce more complex material into the curriculum.

However, the organization of interactive lessons presents certain challenges. These methods can be time-consuming, and not all students have access to the necessary support for effective participation. When dealing with complex topics, students may struggle to fully comprehend and address the material, requiring greater teacher involvement. The presence of weaker students in group settings can sometimes lead to lower scores for even the stronger students.

Conclusion

Interactive teaching methods create a supportive and engaging learning environment that empowers students to take ownership of their education. These methods foster a collaborative atmosphere where students can freely exchange ideas, share knowledge, and work together to overcome challenges.

Interactive lessons encourage open discussions, problem-solving through collective effort, and a mutual exchange of information. Students become active participants, demonstrating their understanding and inspiring each other, leading to a sense of accomplishment and shared learning. This immersive experience captivates

students, making them lose track of time as they delve deeper into the subject matter. Ultimately, interactive teaching methods empower students to fully grasp and master the content of their education.

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